

USING INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IN ARTWORK ANALYSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477814>

Annotation

The article talks about the importance of integration in the education system. In literary education, certain recommendations are given for studying the work "Chol va dengiz" using the integration method.

Key words: Educational system, plot, integration, interdisciplinary integration, history information and communication technologies, comparative analysis, audio-video tape, visual arts, drawing, music, natural science

In the era of rapid development of science, unprecedented developments are being observed in every field, especially innovations in the educational process are a vivid example of this. The goal of all the disciplines organized today is to form knowledge of specific fields in the minds of students and to influence and enrich their spiritual world. There is no field that can match fiction in this task. Because literature has a stronger aesthetic effect on people than other sciences.

The process of integration in literary education takes place in interdisciplinarity. "Integrated education and interdisciplinary communication are two concepts that complement each other. Interdisciplinary communication refers to communication established between academic subjects in order to allow the student to understand this or that problem as deeply as possible in the process of mastering certain knowledge and effectively put the acquired knowledge into practice. When an explanation is given on a topic, the topic is not only explained in one field, but the feelings of the content of that topic are revealed based on psychological, events and geographical, biological, botanical, historical knowledge and based on human feelings.

affects the development of aspects such as thinking, feeling, and being sad. As each science is formed and develops on the basis of interrelationship, in order to study one science in depth, it is necessary to create an understanding by comparing it to other sciences.

This year, school textbooks have a completely new interpretation. In particular, 6th, 7th, 10th, and 11th grade literature books were reprinted. It can

be seen that the curriculum of the textbooks consists of folklore, classic and modern literature, as well as epic works of various genres belonging to world literature. For example, in the newly published 7th grade literature textbook, at the end of each chapter, the analysis of the works created by the creator is explained by connecting it with a certain branch of science after it has been fully mastered by the students. For example, during the first quarter, students will get acquainted with the stories of world and Uzbek authors: Ernest Seton Thompson: the story "Lobo", Normurod Norqabilov: the story "Aqboyin", Ernest Hemingway's stories "The Old Man and the Sea". After the topic is fully mastered, at the end of the chapter, the relationship between literature and natural science is explained on the example of these works. During the second quarter, after getting acquainted with poetry and lyrics, the connection of literature with music, in the third quarter, works such as "Mehrobdan Chayan" by Abdulla Qadiri, "Starry Nights" by Pirimkul Kadirov are studied and the connection of literature with the science of history is explained.

Therefore, it was considered that interdisciplinary integration occurs under the influence of the connection of one discipline with other disciplines. If this direction is considered at the scale of the works, it will be possible to explain it on the example of Ernest Hemingway's work "The Old Man and the Sea", which is taken as the main object of the article.

According to the plan drawn up on the basis of the literary science curriculum of general secondary schools, in the 7th grade, 3 hours were allocated to study the life and work of Ernest Hemingway, and we found it appropriate to divide it as follows:

1. Ernest Hemingway's life and work. Working with the tasks of the "Preparing to read the work" stage - 1 hour
2. Ernest Hemingway: The story "The Old Man and the Sea": Work with the text of the work - 1 hour
3. Working with the tasks of the "Let's discuss" phase of the work. Symbol. Project - 1 hour

During the 1st hour of the lesson, the information about Ernest Hemingway's biography and creative activity will be narrated using electronic exhibition-slides based on information and communication tools, prepared on the following topics and tested by creative literature teachers. serves to be. In this, we will be able to see the connection of literature with informatics and media literacy.

Working on the text of the short story "The Old Man and the Sea", the 2nd hour of the lesson devoted to its analysis begins with the presentation of a video

scene prepared based on this story (showing the work to the students through a film helps to form the characters participating in it in the mind of the child and to create a strong excitement and interest in the example of this work of art causes it to be read with). After the attention of the students is concentrated, the analysis is started based on the comparison of the video scene and the text of the story (plot). Because, as the Methodist scientist S. Matjonov pointed out: "If the analysis of the works in the historical context is not connected with history, and the analysis of the screened works is not connected with the art of cinema, then the desired result cannot be achieved, just as the character of the literary heroes, If we do not rely on the achievements of the sciences of ethics and psychology when talking about their conflicting relations, there will be no consensus. In our opinion, the issue should be put in such a way that students understand that it is impossible to understand and analyze a work of art without theoretical knowledge."

Analyzing this story, the story of the work is not very complicated, at first glance it seems that it consists of only four characters: an old man, a boy, a sea, and a shark. But the reader who has fully understood the work and is able to understand its essence will be far from such an opinion. Because the story is built on a deep philosophical basis, every detail

used appropriately. Here, only the four images listed above have a profound effect on the construction and culmination of the work. The characters of the main characters of the story: old man Santiago, Manolin, the sea, and the shark can be analyzed based on the following plan:

The image of the "old man" in the play served to shape every person today; child - hope for tomorrow; sea - intense life; and sharks are obstacles. That is, the work is analyzed as follows: the old man embarked on a sea journey alone (we also go on the journey of life alone), the old man is caught in the sea with predatory sharks in order to survive (man is found only because of life's difficulties, only those who overcome them will take), as a result of long-term struggles with monsters, the old man becomes mentally exhausted, starts thinking about giving up, at the same time he remembers his student Manolin, whose determination gives the old man strength again gives him confidence and hope for tomorrow).

Explaining the story in connection with a real-life example - evidence serves to show that it is alive, believable, and eternal. Because a good work is open to many interpretations. The stronger the work, the more it can be interpreted and each new generation of readers can have its own old man and sea.

After the plot and symbols of the work are explained by the teacher, the students are given the task of quoting evidence from the story as proof of their opinion and integrating it into another subject or field. In the process of in-depth analysis of the images in the work, they are rooted in historical and mythological images, they are based on legends, in addition, the strategic arts of the old man in the process of fishing, the portrait of the sea, the sea, the old man in the creation of images, or in the image of nature, the sea, are perfectly unique from landscape art. we will be able to see what is used. If the question of how to explain the work in connection with visual art, that is, the science of drawing, will help the students through such presented images, no matter what grade the student is regardless, after reading the work, he is given the task of drawing a picture using the images presented in it, and the child creates a drawing in a state where he feels the task not only with the impression of the text, but also with his imagination. For example, if a child imagines an old man with an old man with swollen hands and a humble face, in the analysis of the interpretation of images, he will try to incorporate his own appearance into the image. In addition, we know that in the work we can see not only people, but also nature and animal world. So, the reader visualizes the image of nature and the animal world through the work. This proves that the story "The Old Man and the Sea" is perfectly created and a rare work.

Finally, during the 3rd hour of the lesson, the tasks of the "Let's discuss" phase will be completed. In this process, it is advisable to conduct a conversation with the students using the questions given in the textbook:

1. What idea (or ideas) did you understand from the story "The Old Man and the Sea"? What do you think are the reasons why the work won the Nobel Prize?
2. Another famous American writer, winner of the Nobel Prize in Literature, William Faulkner called Hemingway "a writer born from defeats." To what extent does this description match the events of the story "The Old Man and the Sea" that you have read? Explain your thoughts based on the text.
3. Why does the author call the main character "old man" and not by his name (Santiago)? Why is the play called "The Old Man and the Sea"?
4. What was the old man's purpose in going on such a long and dangerous sea hunt? Did he achieve his goal? Explain your opinion based on the text.

In short, the correct organization of literary education using the advanced, time-tested and tested theories of the world, different approaches to the problem during the completion of assignments, offering various solutions, integration with other disciplines serves to form the skills of listening and

learning from each other as a team, and the development of the student's critical thinking.

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